

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.5 – Bundle of digital twin tools for net zero decision-making 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>D3.5 presents the second bundle of digital twin tools developed in UP2030 to support net-zero and circular urban planning. It integrates an Urban Building Energy Modelling (UBEM) and AI framework, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) module, the MIRA Digital Twin platform, and the Circular Urban Planning tool into a shared data architecture for building- and district-scale analysis. The Istanbul pilot demonstrates how combined envelope upgrades, heat pumps and rooftop photovoltaics can reduce energy use, lower CO₂ emissions, improve indoor thermal comfort and, under favourable tariff and grid conditions, deliver attractive economic performance. In parallel, the Circular Urban Planning tool shows how material stocks and flows can guide selective deconstruction and reuse strategies. The deliverable outlines replication requirements and governance needs, positioning the toolkit as a scalable support for climate-neutral city pathways.</p>			

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Executive summary

Deliverable D3.5 presents the second consolidated bundle of digital twin tools developed in UP2030 to support evidence-based, net-zero decision-making in cities. Its purpose is to document the final integration of four complementary tools—the Urban Building Energy Modelling (UBEM) system, the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) module, the MIRA Digital Twin platform, and the Circular Urban Planning tool—into a coherent architecture enabling multi-scale, cross-sectoral urban sustainability assessments.

The deliverable outlines how these tools communicate through a shared data environment, how they support urban retrofitting and circularity planning, and how they contribute to climate-neutral strategies in line with UP2030 objectives.

The integrated toolkit allows cities to assess energy performance, emissions, material flows and circularity potentials through complementary and harmonised workflows that support informed decision-making. The UBEM system provides long-term, building-level energy simulations supported by AI and GIS, which are then assessed through the LCA module to evaluate embodied and operational environmental impacts in line with EU standards. These results are brought together and explored within the MIRA Digital Twin platform, which acts as the front-end environment where planners, policymakers and other stakeholders can interactively compare scenarios at building and district scale through an intuitive, map-based interface. In parallel, the Circular Urban Planning tool is used as a standalone but complementary application to analyse material stocks, reuse potential and circularity strategies, guiding decisions on selective deconstruction, refurbishment priorities and the development of relevant supply chains. By using these tools together, city stakeholders can explore energy, environmental and circularity impacts within a single, coherent decision-support process, avoiding fragmented analyses and disconnected results, and instead working with a consistent evidence base to compare scenarios and agree on prioritised urban transformation strategies.

The Istanbul demonstration provided a full proof-of-concept for the integrated system. Results from simulations of 2,455 buildings show that envelope improvements, heat pump integration, and photovoltaic systems can substantially reduce heating demand, enhance electricity self-sufficiency, mitigate indoor overheating, and lower district-level CO₂ emissions. Scenarios combining TS825/Passivhaus insulation standards with heat pumps and PV systems achieved the highest energy and emissions reductions, though economic feasibility varied due to electricity tariff structures and upfront investment requirements. Analysis also confirmed that future grid decarbonisation is essential: without a declining electricity emission factor, electrification alone may not deliver the expected climate benefits by 2050. The findings demonstrate the value of integrated LCA and UBEM outputs for understanding trade-offs between operational savings, embodied carbon, economic viability, and long-term resilience.

The expected impact for cities extends across operational, strategic, and governance dimensions. Cities gain access to a harmonised digital infrastructure that supports transparent evaluation of retrofit pathways, identification of high-priority interventions, and alignment with climate-neutrality roadmaps. The toolkit enhances municipal capacity to quantify environmental and economic outcomes, supports cross-departmental coordination, and strengthens citizen engagement through visual and accessible digital twin interfaces. By enabling robust scenario modelling and circularity assessments (CAs), the tools directly contribute to better-informed investment decisions, more resilient urban planning strategies, and accelerated progress toward the Mission-100 climate-neutral cities goals.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment METU, ODTUGUNAM, MAG and ETH within WP3. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D 3.4 - Bundle of Digital Twin Tools for Net-Zero Decision-Making 1 D 3.2 - Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2	D 3.3 - Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 3

The recipients of this deliverable's content are both technical and non-technical stakeholders involved in the UP2030 Project. In particular, it is addressed to technical developers and implementation teams, who can use the document as a functional guideline to understand the tools developed under the Net-Zero Urban Districts framework, their technical setup, data requirements and integration logic.

In addition, the deliverable is intended for city authorities, urban planners and project liaisons engaged in strategic planning and decision-making processes within participating cities. This final version includes results obtained in tools testing in cities and provides useful information to cities and liaisons, containing the data required for using the tools and an overview of the results provided for each tool and the bundle itself for developing the decarbonisation and climate mitigation plan in urban districts.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CA	Circularity Assessment
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CIBSE	The Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers
CIM	City Information Modelling
CTE DB HE	CTE – Código Técnico de la Edificación (Spanish Building Technical Code) DB – Documento Básico (Basic Document) HE – Ahorro de Energía (Energy Saving)
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
HP	Heat Pump
IOD	Indoor Overheating Degree
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MFA	Material stocks and Flows Analysis
NPV	Net Present Value
NZEB	Nearly Zero-Energy Building
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System

PV	Photovoltaic
ROI	Return On Investment
SQL	Structured Query Language
TSL/SSL	Transport Layer Security / Secure Sockets Layer
TS825	Turkish Thermal Insulation Requirements for Buildings
UBEM	Urban Building Energy Modelling

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this document is to define the integration framework for Building Information Modelling (BIM) -based data and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) workflows within the UP2030 project. It outlines how digital tools and data exchange mechanisms will support urban sustainability objectives, focusing on energy efficiency, circularity, and emission reduction strategies. The scope includes the description of technical requirements, interoperability standards, and data flows necessary to enable seamless communication between modules such as BIM, LCA, and the MIRA platform. This technical framework description includes the system architecture, data-flow design, shared database structure, and communication protocols that allow these tools to operate as independent services while contributing to a unified analytical workflow.

The scope also includes considerations related to data governance, long-term data preservation, and the application of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles. The integration framework is aligned with these principles by ensuring that data are stored in a centralised database with well-defined schemas and metadata, enabling discoverability and controlled access. Interoperability is achieved through standardised data structures, common identifiers, and the use of open and recognised standards, while reusability is supported through version control, traceability of changes, and preservation strategies that facilitate replication in other urban contexts and reuse beyond the UP2030 project lifecycle. These principles are critical to ensure that the integration framework can be replicated across different cities and institutional contexts, as they provide a common foundation for consistent data exchange and tool interoperability. They also enable the future integration of newly developed analytical tools by ensuring that data, interfaces and methodologies remain reusable, extensible and compatible over time.

This document serves as a reference for project partners, city stakeholders, and mainly technical teams involved in implementing digital tools in cities. It ensures alignment with the project's broader goals of promoting climate-neutral cities and provides guidance for replicating the integration approach in other urban contexts.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised into five main sections. Following the **Section 1** covering the introduction, **Section 2** presents the technical integration framework, detailing the final architecture, data exchange protocols, and tools interoperability, including knowledge requirements and data communication standards. These technical requirements include the use of a shared and centralised data hub, secure authentication and role-based access control, service-oriented interactions between independent analytical modules, and the ability to support asynchronous processing and scenario-based updates.

Section 3 focuses on Material stocks and Flow Analysis (MFA), LCA, and circularity assessment (CA) methodologies applied within the project Lisbon pilot. **Section 4** provides an assessment of energy and emission reductions achieved through the Istanbul demonstration and evaluates the impact on urban planning and decision-making processes. **Section 5** outlines conclusions, recommendations, replication potential, and future research opportunities, ensuring scalability and long-term relevance. References and supporting materials are included at the end for further consultation.

2 Integration framework: Final architecture and data exchange

This section presents the final integration framework that brings together the UP2030 digital tools into a coherent and interoperable architecture capable of supporting city-scale energy, emissions and CAs. It explains how city and building data are processed through different analytical tools and brought together in a shared digital environment to support informed urban decision-making as can be seen in the following Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the dataflow between tools integration

The framework describes how the Urban Building Energy Modelling (UBEM)–Artificial Intelligence (AI) engine, the LCA module and the MIRA Digital Twin platform interact through shared standards, harmonised datasets and a centralised data hub. Through this coordinated workflow, static building information is transformed into energy performance results and subsequently into environmental and circularity indicators, which are then made accessible to end users through intuitive visualisations. This approach enables scenario-based analyses, automated updates and consistent comparison of results across different planning options.

In practical terms, this means that a city stakeholder can explore different renovation scenarios—such as improving insulation or introducing heat pumps—and understand how these choices affect energy consumption and CO₂ emissions at both building and district level. By viewing these results on interactive maps and dashboards, users can compare options, identify trade-offs and support discussions around long-term climate and net-zero objectives.

By establishing clear interoperability rules, data governance procedures and service-oriented interactions, the integration architecture forms the backbone of the UP2030 decision-support environment and provides a replicable model for other cities seeking to adopt digital twins for climate-neutral planning. The following Table 1 provides an overview of the main digital tools and components involved in the UP2030 Digital Tools integration framework, summarising their respective roles, the key data they exchange, and the technical and interoperability requirements that enable their coordination. This overview is intended to support a clear understanding of how the different tools interact within the overall architecture, before the detailed description of the data-flow design presented in the subsequent sections.

Table 1. Technical requirements and interoperability overview

<i>Tool / Component</i>	<i>Role in the framework</i>	<i>Key data exchanged</i>	<i>Interoperability standards and formats</i>	<i>Technical requirements</i>
<i>Circular Urban Planning Tool (MFA-LCA-CA)¹</i>	Assessment of material stocks, flows and circularity potential at urban scale; identification of priority materials and buildings for reuse and selective deconstruction	Building material quantities, material typologies, environmental impact indicators (GHG), circularity metrics	GIS-based data structures (QGIS), tabular datasets (CSV, Excel), compatibility with BIM-derived material inventories	Standalone QGIS plugin; requires access to building material datasets; potential integration via shared database or standardised material tables
<i>UBEM-AI Engine</i>	Energy performance simulation and scenario generation	Energy demand, PV generation, thermal indicators	Structured tables, standard units (SI)	Read/write access to shared database, asynchronous execution
<i>LCA Module</i>	Environmental impact assessment and aggregation	Embodied and operational carbon indicators, environmental KPIs	IFC (materials), ILCD / EF 3.0 conventions, ISO 14040/44	Harmonised methodological assumptions, containerised services
<i>MIRA Digital Twin Platform</i>	Visualisation and stakeholder interaction	Building-level and district-level indicators	SQL queries, GIS-compatible data structures	Read-only access, scalable front-end, user authentication
<i>BIM / CIM inputs</i>	Source of geometric and material information	Geometry, materials, assemblies	IFC, CityGML, CityJSON	Standardised export formats, consistent identifiers
<i>Central Data Hub (PostgreSQL)</i>	Common data layer and synchronization point	Building data, scenarios, energy results, LCA indicators	Relational schema, unique IDs, SQL	Centralised database, role-based access, secure connections (TLS/SSL)

¹ Although the Circular Urban Planning tool is not currently integrated into the UP2030 data hub, its reliance on standardised building material data and open-source GIS formats makes it technically compatible with the existing integration framework and suitable for future integration.

2.1 Data flows architecture

The overall data-flow architecture is organized around a central online PostgreSQL database that acts as the common data hub between the UBEM-AI tool, the LCA module and the user interface tool. The architecture follows a loosely coupled, service-oriented pattern where each module runs as an independent service, with its own execution logic and update cycles, while remaining synchronized through well-defined read/write operations on shared tables. This design supports asynchronous processing, scalable execution at building and district level, and a clear separation between computation (back-end services) and visualisation (front-end).

In practical terms, this architecture means that all tools exchange information through a common database rather than through direct, point-to-point connections. Each tool reads the data it needs and writes its results back to the same data hub, ensuring consistency, traceability, and transparency across the entire workflow.

The PostgreSQL instance is deployed on Azure (*up2030scenarios.postgres.database.azure.com*) and is exposed only to authenticated and authorized components within the project environment. All components connect directly to this managed PostgreSQL service, which centralises data storage and ensures that all modules operate on a consistent and up-to-date representation of the building stock and renovation scenarios.

At schema level (see Figure 2), the database is structured around three main tables:

- The *buildings_units* table stores the static description of the building stock, including identifiers, geometry (e.g. floor area and envelope areas), basic construction characteristics and location. This information does not change per scenario; it represents the current situation of the city district and only needs to be updated if the underlying building stock changes, for example, when new buildings are added or when the municipal dataset is expanded.
- The *scenarios* table holds the catalogue of predefined renovation scenarios, including the specific characteristics of each one (target envelope performance, airtightness objectives and PV/battery configuration) as well as the aggregated environmental key performance indicators (KPIs) for long-term LCA analysis, in particular for 2025 and 2050. As in the previous table, additional scenarios can be defined and inserted into this table so that they are automatically incorporated into the analysis and made available for visualisation through the user interface.
- The *building_per_scenario* table contains the results for each building–scenario combination, where energy performance indicators and environmental indicators are progressively added by the analytical modules. Likewise, if new buildings or scenarios are added, this table is updated so that all combinations can be reflected in the subsequent analyses and visualisation.

Figure 2. Database schema and main tables used for data exchange across analytical modules

Access to analytical base is controlled through clearly separated roles:

- Two write-enabled service accounts are used by the back-end processing services (UBEM and LCA) to insert and update scenarios, energy-performance results and LCA results, including their aggregation. These accounts have permission to insert and update records in the relevant tables.
- Read-only roles are defined for the user interface (and for any additional consumers, if required). These roles are restricted to SELECT operations and cannot modify the contents of the database.

All connections use the standard PostgreSQL protocol over encrypted channels (TLS/SSL), as configured in the Azure service, and users connect directly to the managed PostgreSQL instance using their individual database credentials.

The data flow between tools, represented in Figure 3, follows a staged pipeline:

1. **Static data ingestion.** Building data from external sources are pre-processed and imported into *building_units*. On the other hand, the baseline and renovation scenarios on which the analysis will be performed are defined and stored in the *scenarios* table.
2. **Energy performance assessment and storage of results.** UBEM-AI reads the required input from *building_units* and *scenarios*, executes the long-term energy simulations and energy performance assessments, and then writes the corresponding outputs to *building_per_scenario*. For each (*building_id*, *scenario_id*) pair, it creates or updates the

corresponding records such as annual heating and cooling demand, lighting consumption, or PV generation. As mentioned before, running these simulations requires specialized modelling expertise and significant computational effort, which is why their execution is managed exclusively by the back-end services rather than being triggered synchronously from the user interface.

3. **LCA assessment and enrichment of results** The LCA module then operates on the same *building_per_scenario* table. It retrieves the energy indicators and the building information stored in *building_units*, combines them with the project’s environmental datasets and computes embodied and operational impact indicators at building level. These calculations take into account renovation materials, differences in operating schedules and the energy savings associated with each scenario. The resulting CO₂ and other environmental impact metrics are written into additional fields of the corresponding records in the *building_per_scenario* table, which therefore becomes the consolidated view that integrates both energy and environmental performance for each building–scenario combination. After completing the building-level assessment, the module aggregates the results across all buildings for each scenario and stores these aggregated environmental KPIs in the *scenarios* table, providing a clear summary of the scenario-level outcomes.
4. **Consumption by the Digital Twin front-end.** The user interface accesses the PostgreSQL database in read-only mode. It queries *building_units*, *scenarios* and *building_per_scenario* to construct the visualisations presented to end users. The main functionalities of the interface and the way these results are rendered are described in section 2.3.

To keep the system synchronized, a background cron job is deployed. This job monitors changes in *building_per_scenario* and *scenarios* tables (new buildings, updated parameters, newly defined scenarios) and triggers the execution of the energy and LCA pipelines for the affected records. Once calculations finish, the corresponding entries in *building_per_scenario* are updated automatically, ensuring that all visualisations in the front-end always reflect the latest available information.

Figure 3. End-to-end data-flow architecture connecting static inputs, UBEM simulations, LCA assessment and front-end visualisation

In summary, this data-flow architecture provides a robust and transparent mechanism for linking UBEM-AI simulations, LCA calculations and interactive visualisation. By centralising data management in a single PostgreSQL instance and clearly separating read and write responsibilities, the system ensures consistency, scalability and secure integration of all tools developed within the project.

2.2 [Knowledge requirements for analytical services](#)

In this subsection, the knowledge prerequisites for use the analytical services provided by METU/GUNAM and CIRCE are described.

2.2.1 [UBEM:AI- Powered decision-making tool for decarbonisation](#)

This tool is built on three key enabling technologies: UBEM, AI, and GIS. UBEM enables the long-term calculation of the energy performance and thermal comfort of zones and buildings at the urban scale using high-resolution data for the years 2025 and 2050. By doing so, it allows the analysis of different what-if scenarios. Developing these models, collecting input data, and running simulations require modelling expertise. The datasets generated through this process are then used to train AI models. To adjust parameters and obtain predictions at the city scale quickly, AI models make it possible for users to quickly adjust parameters and obtain predictions at the city scale. While the current model is calibrated for the specific case study, the transfer learning method previously developed by METU would be used for different urban contexts and climatic zones in future applications.

The GIS infrastructure provides an interactive and dynamic interface through which users can easily analyse renovation scenarios and their long-term impacts (2025 and 2050) using KPIs—environmental, economic, and thermal comfort. Users can compare scenarios simply by interacting with static and dynamic visualisations (3D maps, interactive scatter plots, static charts, etc.). The only prerequisite for users is understanding what each scenario represents; these explanations are clearly provided within the interface. To evaluate the tool's usability and gather user feedback, workshops were conducted with municipalities and local authorities, and the insights gained from these sessions were incorporated into the design process.

If the purpose of the tool, where it was developed, what it calculates, and what can be analysed are briefly explained to different user groups, then users will be able to use the tool independently via the interface/website links provided to them. This describes the stand-alone use of the tool.

Within the project, the tool developed by MAGGIOLI (the digital twin environment) integrates UBEM with CIRCE's tool, creating a bundle of tools. In this integrated version, the renovation results and baseline building performance calculated through the UBEM model can be viewed in MAGGIOLI's interface using a 2D map and interactive infographic panels that appear upon selecting a building. Although this integration currently relies on static simulation data, it establishes the necessary foundation for incorporating real-time information in future iterations of the digital twin.

2.2.2 [Life Cycle Assessment \(LCA\) module](#)

The LCA module operates within the Digital Twin environment through harmonised data communication principles, open standards, and consistent methodological requirements that ensure robust environmental assessment at both building and district scale. Data exchange relies on interoperable formats that integrate smoothly with BIM and City Information Modelling (CIM) models, including IFC for geometric, material and constructive attributes, and CityGML or CityJSON for the representation of the wider urban context. Life-cycle inventory information follows ILCD and EF 3.0 conventions, and complementary datasets may be transferred through structured CSV, JSON or XML files. In this module, compatibility with external LCA software is not required, as the environmental database has been fully transferred into the project's Excel-based structure, allowing direct access to all material and process indicators within the integrated workflow.

Once the upstream UBEM-AI module has generated the scenarios, covering building materials, envelope properties, operating schedules, energy system configurations, and the energy performance of each building, the LCA module automatically computes environmental impacts at both the building level and as scenario-wide aggregates. If any of these inputs are updated, the relevant indicators are recomputed to reflect the latest state.

The reliability of the environmental assessment depends on detailed and consistent input data. Material specifications, construction assemblies, operational energy profiles, occupant behaviour and equipment usage are integrated with the spatial granularity provided by BIM and CIM models and the temporal resolution required for operational LCA. For the definition of building envelopes, the module incorporates constructive solutions taken from the official catalogue of details in the Spanish CTE DB HE Energy Saving document. These regulated assemblies ensure that the thermal performance used in operational carbon calculations reflects realistic and nationally compliant building behaviour. For embodied carbon assessment, the environmental profiles of materials are based on the Ökobaudat database, which provides harmonised and verified life cycle inventory data consistent with European LCA standards.

Methodological consistency is maintained through alignment with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, the systematic use of SI units and European norms, and unique identifiers that allow accurate cross referencing of building components between the Digital Twin models and the LCA datasets. All computations are carried out through containerised server-side services with parallel processing capabilities to support district scale scenario analysis. A comprehensive data governance framework, including version control, traceability of changes and systematic validation checks, ensures transparency and compliance with European requirements for environmental reporting.

2.3 User interface: Overview of the MIRA Platform:

The MIRA Digital Twin platform provides an intuitive, map-based environment where users can explore building-level and district-level information on emissions and retrofit potential. Designed for a broad range of urban actors, from planners and engineers to policymakers and citizens, the interface brings together spatial data, simulation outputs and real-time indicators in a way that is approachable even for non-technical users.

At its core, MIRA visualises a virtual representation of the city, integrating building footprints and energy-related parameters. In the Istanbul pilot, the platform displayed data for 2,460 buildings in the Kadıköy district, enabling users to examine the current building stock and explore what-if scenarios related to insulation, heat pumps, rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems, and combined interventions. The interface communicates this information through coloured map layers, building-specific pop-ups, and aggregated district-level metrics.

2.3.1 User Interface and Functionalities

The user interface is built around several essential visual elements. First, a scalable urban map provides a geospatial view of all assets included in the digital twin. Users can zoom, pan, filter, and select buildings or groups of buildings to investigate their attributes. Second, side panels give access to scenario controls, simulation results, and metadata. Third, dynamic charts and numeric outputs present comparative insights, such as shifts in heating consumption, cooling demand, or CO₂ emissions between the baseline condition and future retrofit scenarios. Together, these features allow MIRA to function as both an analytical workspace and a communication tool for broader stakeholder engagement.

The MIRA platform combines multiple functionalities that support data exploration, scenario evaluation, and strategic planning. Its core capabilities include:

2.3.1.1 *Spatial Visualisation and Asset Profiling*

Each building within the pilot area is represented as an interactive object on the map. Clicking on a building reveals its profile, which includes (Figure 4):

- Estimated baseline heating and cooling energy consumption
- Energy performance indicators such as kWh/m²

- Rooftop solar potential

Figure 4. Profile for each building analysed

Profiles are derived from data provided by METU and ODTUGUNAM and standardised within MIRA to maintain interoperability across modules. More information could also be stored, as:

- Footprint area and height;
- Construction period;
- Building type (residential, mixed-use, commercial);

and many more. The interactive representation of individual buildings encourages user engagement by allowing users to directly explore and interrogate the characteristics and performance of specific assets. By clicking on buildings and accessing their profiles, users can actively navigate the data rather than passively viewing aggregated results, supporting a more intuitive understanding of local conditions and priorities.

2.3.1.2 Scenario Simulation Integration

A key functionality of MIRA is its ability to visualise data produced by external simulation engines. In the Istanbul case, METU and ODTUGUNAM conducted energy retrofit simulations for four scenarios:

- Envelope Improvement (Turkish Thermal Insulation Requirements for Buildings (TS825) Standard)
- Passivhaus Improvement
- TS825 + Heat Pump
- Passivhaus + Heat Pump

MIRA receives these outputs from the database, rendering them instantly on the map. For each scenario, the user interface displays:

- Heating and cooling consumption before and after renovation
- Expected energy savings
- Estimated reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions
- Performance metrics for short-term (2030) and long-term (2050) projections

The platform accommodates unlimited simulations, remaining agnostic to the modelling tool, methodology, or algorithm used. This functionality provides the user with the ability to compare multiple renovation scenarios and immediately observe their effects on energy consumption and emissions. This interactive scenario exploration enables users to test “what-if” options, compare outcomes, and develop a clearer understanding of the trade-offs associated with different intervention strategies.

2.3.1.3 Aggregated District-Level Indicators

Beyond single-building analysis, the interface visualises collective impacts of retrofit strategies across the district. Users can compare total energy demand, scenario-wide CO₂ reductions, or overall efficiency improvements. These aggregated views support municipal-level planning and reporting processes. Engagement at the strategic level is supported by aggregated district-wide indicators, which allow users to move from individual buildings to a broader urban perspective. By switching between scenarios and viewing collective impacts, users can explore how local actions scale up to district-level outcomes, supporting collaborative discussion and evidence-based planning.

2.3.1.4 Communication and Engagement Tools

Communication and engagement tools play a crucial role within the MIRA platform, as they transform complex simulation outputs into accessible and intuitive insights for a wide range of stakeholders. By visualising energy, environmental and scenario-based results through clear maps, charts and comparative panels, the platform helps bridge the gap between technical analysis and public understanding.

This tool supports not only internal decision-making among municipal departments and technical experts, but also broader engagement processes, enabling planners, policymakers and citizens to discuss retrofit options, understand trade-offs and co-develop pathways toward climate neutrality. In this way, MIRA functions not only as an analytical environment but also as a communication interface that strengthens transparency, inclusiveness and collaboration throughout the planning process.

Maps and visuals generated by MIRA are accessible, compelling, and suitable for public communication. This enables the platform to:

- Support multi-departmental decision meetings
- Illustrate urban data during citizen engagement sessions
- Increase transparency by showing the benefits of retrofitting measures

Accessibility for different stakeholder groups is a key design principle of the MIRA platform. The interface is structured to support a wide range of users, from technical experts to non-technical stakeholders such as experts, political leaders, and community members. By combining intuitive map-based navigation, clear visual cues, and simplified indicators. Advanced users can access detailed data and scenario comparisons, while non-technical users can focus on high-level insights and visual summaries without requiring specialised knowledge.

2.3.2 Access Procedures and Visualisation of Results

The process for accessing and using the MIRA platform involves several steps that ensure data integrity, user authentication, and smooth engagement with the tool. While access procedures may be adapted per city, the Istanbul pilot followed a structured workflow that reflects the general MIRA approach.

2.3.2.1 Accessing the Platform

Users typically access MIRA through a secure web-based interface (Figure 5). Login credentials are supplied to authorised municipal staff, researchers, and project partners. Authentication is handled by MIRA's governance layer, which ensures:

- Secure data access
- Compliance with privacy and confidentiality requirements
- User-specific permissions (e.g., basic viewer vs. advanced GIS user)

Once logged in, users arrive on the main dashboard, where key navigation elements guide them toward datasets, layers, and scenario modules.

Figure 5. Login page in MIRA platform

2.3.2.2 Loading the Case Study Area

After selecting the Istanbul/Kadıköy environment, the interface loads the full dataset of 2,454 buildings. The user can choose between:

- Baseline view (current state)
- Scenario view (2030 or 2050)
- Combined comparisons

Loading the dataset activates the geospatial map and side panels containing data summaries.

2.3.2.3 Exploring Building-Level Outputs

Selecting any building (Figure 6) triggers a pop-up card detailing:

- Baseline energy consumption in kWh
- Energy intensity (kWh/m²)
- Post-retrofit values for each scenario
- Changes in heating and cooling demand

- Expected CO₂ savings

These metrics help users quickly understand the impact of individual interventions.

Figure 6. Visualization of the map with the buildings

2.3.2.4 Analysing District-Level Results

Visualisation tools allow users to move from micro-level insights to macro-level dynamics. The interface aggregates building data to show (Figure 7):

- Total district-wide energy consumption
- Total CO₂ emissions before and after retrofitting
- Comparative scenario performance (TS825 vs Passivhaus, with/without heat pumps)

Figure 7. Visualisation of aggregated building data

2.3.2.5 Exporting and Communicating Results

MIRA supports export of:

- Map screenshots for presentations
- Tabular summaries for policy briefs
- Scenario comparisons for technical reporting

These outputs are essential for communication with decision-makers, citizens, and technical units involved in Istanbul's energy transition planning.

In summary, Section 2 outlines the integrated architecture that enables the UP2030 digital tools to operate as a coherent and scalable decision-support ecosystem. The final framework demonstrates how shared data standards, a centralised PostgreSQL database and service-oriented interactions allow UBEM-AI simulations, LCA computations and the MIRA front-end to exchange information seamlessly across modules.

This integration ensures consistency in scenario analysis, supports automated updates as new data become available, and provides users with reliable, high-resolution insights into energy performance, environmental impacts and retrofit potential. Together, these elements establish a robust foundation for evidence-based planning and form the backbone of the project's digital twin approach, enabling cities to explore net-zero pathways in a transparent, interoperable and replicable manner.

3 Circular Urban Planning: Material stocks and flows analysis (MFA), life cycle assessment (LCA) and circularity assessment (CA)

Urban building demolition generates billions of tons of mixed waste, from concrete and structural components to fixtures like windows and sinks. These activities not only contribute to long-term solid waste accumulation but also release pollutants into air, water, and soil, creating health and environmental risks.

Research shows that a significant share of these materials can be reused or recycled, reducing resource consumption in the construction sector. Promoting circular practices could shift urban development from a linear model toward a sustainable urban metabolism. However, implementation is hindered by regulatory gaps, lack of incentives, and underdeveloped supply chains.

To unlock these opportunities, it is essential to identify which materials offer the greatest potential for reuse, which supply chains can support their recovery, and which buildings should be prioritized for selective deconstruction. Targeting high-impact materials and assets ensures efficient resource allocation and maximizes environmental benefits. This strategic approach forms the foundation for the Circular Urban Planning tool.

3.1 The Circular Urban Planning tool

The Circular Urban Planning tool aims to support decision-making process towards improving circularity in built environment through implementation of reuse and recycling strategies at urban scales. In practice, it consists in a QGIS plugin (Figure 8) that can be used on any city or neighbourhood. It can be easily downloaded and install from the GitHub repository. It was developed at the Chair of Circular Engineering for Architecture at the ETH Zürich.

It is included in Bundle of digital twin tools for net zero decision-making as a standalone tool with is complementary to the others as it provides information on the materials available in the city and addresses the question of circularity of those materials.

Figure 8. Interface of the tool integrated in QGIS

The objective of the tool is to identify the most relevant materials and building parts to reuse considering their environmental impact. Using the data provided by the cities the tool evaluates the elements, regarding GHG emissions, and circular strategies that can be the most beneficial to reuse or recycle from a GHG emissions point of view. In the end, the tool provides information on which supply

chains should be developed to prepare the selective deconstruction of buildings as well as their refurbishment. The Circular Urban Planning is a modelling framework with a bottom-up approach, which integrates MFA over time, into the new parametric model that LCA and CA).

3.2 Further uses

The tool can be applied to any city or neighbourhood, provided that some data on the materials of the buildings is available, and thus is easily scalable to different regions. Its flexibility allows urban planners and researchers to adapt it to different contexts without major technical barriers.

It is also open-source and freely accessible on GitHub, ensuring transparency and encouraging collaboration among stakeholders. This openness makes it possible for municipalities, research institutions, and private actors to integrate the tool into their workflows without licensing restrictions.

Finally, adapting the tool to new case studies is straightforward. Only minor edits to the hypothesis spreadsheet are required to reflect local building characteristics and material assumptions, making the process efficient and scalable for diverse urban environments.

4 Assessment and impact analysis of tools implementation

4.1 Assessment of Energy and Emission Reductions: Results of the Istanbul Demonstration

For Istanbul, the pilot area is selected, consisting of 2,455 buildings and 12,016 zones including residential units and offices, most of which are high-density, mid-rise structures typically between four and six stories. The majority were built before 1980, reflecting an aging building stock that leads to poor overall energy performance in the neighbourhood.

The simulations were held for each year (2025 and 2050) using EnergyPlus software at annual, monthly, and hourly time steps. UBEM is based on two main data types: geometric and semantic, which enable the creation of detailed energy models. The 3D building geometries are acquired from the city GIS database, buildings' Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), and the National Address Inquiry System. Semantic data refers to the structured non-geometric information required for energy modelling. This includes building- and zone-level attributes such as envelope U-values, system efficiency parameters, and internal loads (e.g., equipment power densities, lighting power densities, and setpoints).

The typical meteorological year (TMY) file for Istanbul (W2025) is used for baseline simulations reflecting current climate conditions. To assess future climate impacts, a new 2050 weather file (W2050) is generated using the Future Weather Generator. After completion of the simulations, hourly energy consumption data for heating, cooling, equipment, and lighting are extracted for subsequent analysis. To ensure accuracy, the models are calibrated against EPCs and actual natural gas billing data. The calibrated models constitute the **Baseline Scenario**, representing the current energy performance of the building stock.

The energy renovation scenarios are developed, and their effectiveness is evaluated using the KPIs. There are three main categories of energy renovation scenarios that aim to achieve the following:

- Reducing energy use with passive and active systems,
- Mitigate indoor overheating degree (IOD)
- Transitioning to high-efficiency, electrified active energy systems,
- Generating on-site energy from renewable systems.

Passive system scenarios: Based on the TS825 and the Passivhaus standards, these scenarios enhance envelope insulation to minimize heating and cooling loads.

Active system scenarios: Introduce heat pump (HP) technologies for both heating and cooling, enabling electrification and supporting the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy.

Renewable energy system scenarios: Evaluate rooftop PV potential to meet buildings' electricity consumption.

In line with this categorization, several energy renovation scenarios (Figure 9) have been evaluated:

- Baseline, representing the current building stock.
- ENVE_{TS}, where insulation is improved (U_{wall} , U_{roof} , U_{window} , U_{ground}) based on the TS825 standard;
- ENVE_{PAS}, where insulation is improved (U_{wall} , U_{roof} , U_{window} , U_{ground}) based on the Passivhaus standard;
- HP, where natural gas boilers are replaced with heat pumps for both heating and cooling;
- ENVE_{TS+HP}, where heat pumps are combined with the ENVETS scenario;
- ENVE_{PAS+HP}, where heat pumps are combined with the ENVEPAS scenario.

In addition, the scenarios ENVE_{TS}+PV, ENVE_{PAS}+PV, ENVE_{TS}+HP+PV, and ENVE_{PAS}+HP+PV denote the same strategies as above but with the inclusion of PV systems to further enhance the clean energy transition.

Code	Envelope Retrofit	Heat Pump	Photovoltaic Panel	
Baseline	X	X	X	Category Scenarios
ENVE _{TS}	TS825	X	X	
ENVE _{PAS}	Passive House	X	X	
HP	X	✓	X	
PV	X	X	✓	
ENVE _{TS} + HP	TS825	✓	X	Combined Scenarios
ENVE _{PAS} + HP	Passive House	✓	X	
HP + PV	X	✓	✓	
ENVE _{TS} + PV	TS825	X	✓	
ENVE _{PAS} + PV	Passive House	X	✓	
ENVE _{TS} + HP + PV	TS825	✓	✓	
ENVE _{PAS} + HP + PV	Passive House	✓	✓	

Figure 9. Categories of energy renovation scenarios

4.2 Environmental and Economic KPIs

KPIs for each scenario are calculated, which are classified into three main categories: environmental, economic, and thermal comfort indicators (Figure 10). Environmental indicators serve as critical metrics for evaluating how much a building contributes to environmental impacts through its energy consumption and associated emissions. Thermal comfort indicators capture indoor environmental quality from the occupants’ perspective. Economic indicators provide insight into the financial viability and investment performance of the proposed measures. KPIs identify the strategies that show the highest decarbonisation impact relative to investment costs. This quantitative evidence enables policymakers to prioritize cost-effective measures and design regulatory frameworks tailored to the specific needs of the existing building stock.

Figure 10. Categorization of KPIs

Environmental Indicators

- **Heating Energy Consumption (kWh/m²):** the amount of energy used to heat a space to an indoor setpoint temperature. It is calculated by considering the efficiency of the heating equipment.

- Cooling Energy Consumption (kWh/m²): the amount of energy used to cool a space to an indoor setpoint temperature. It is calculated by considering the efficiency of the cooling equipment.
- CO₂ Reduction (tCO₂eq): the decrease in carbon dioxide emissions achieved when renovation scenarios are applied to the building.
- PV-Based Electricity Production (kWh): the amount of electricity generated through rooftop PV systems.
- Electricity Self-Sufficiency Index: the ratio between PV-based electricity generation and building electricity energy demand.
- Emission Calculations: Annual CO₂ emissions are calculated by multiplying the annual energy consumption of each source by its respective emission factor. For natural gas, fixed emission factors are adopted from international authorities such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Electricity CO₂ emissions are quantified by multiplying end-use energy with time-varying emission factors obtained from, ETKB (2024), and Enerdata (2025).

Thermal Comfort Indicators

- IOD (°C): the extent and duration by which indoor temperatures exceed a defined comfort threshold, indicating thermal discomfort or potential health risk due to excessive indoor heat. IOD is calculated for the zones that rely only on natural ventilation.

Economic Indicators

- Discounted Payback Period (year): the period of time required for an investment to pay off, considering that future savings are valued slightly less over time.
- Net Present Value (NPV) (€): the present value of the future cash flows generated by the investment, discounted to the present.
- Return On Investment (ROI) (%): the percentage of return on a project based on capital investment and helps to compare different investment options.
- Abatement Cost (€/tCO₂): the cost-efficiency of carbon reductions across scenarios associated with reducing environmental impact, such as investing in energy efficiency renovations and renewable energy integration.

4.2.1 Heating Energy Consumption

Heating demand represents the largest share of total energy consumption in all buildings in the neighbourhood (Figure 11). In heating energy use, there is a consistent downward trend from 2025 to 2050 due to global warming. This corresponds to a reduction of approximately 25%. A closer look into the renovation scenarios shows that heating energy use can be reduced up to threefold through envelope improvements, primarily lowering natural gas consumption. In contrast, the integration of heat pumps shifted the demand from natural gas to electricity and reduced heating energy use by up to 77% across all scenarios, owing to heat pumps' higher coefficient of performance (COP) compared to the efficiency of natural gas boilers.

Figure 11. Energy renovations scenarios

4.2.2 Cooling Energy Consumption

In contrast, the cooling energy use increased by approximately 2.3 times across all scenarios from 2025 to 2050 due to the increasing temperatures (Figure 12). The cooling demand gradually declined 22% from TS to Passivhaus scenarios.

Heat pumps are more efficient than conventional air conditioners and can reduce cooling energy use by approximately 40%. Besides electrification and its potential to be coupled with PV, heat pumps have the additional benefit of meeting both heating and cooling loads in one single piece of equipment.

Figure 12. Cooling renovations scenarios

4.2.3 CO₂ Reduction by Scenario

The analysis of CO₂ emission distributions (Figure 13 and Figure 14) shows how each renovation scenario changes the environmental impact. The Baseline scenario has the highest and widest distribution of emissions, with mean values around 4–5 tonnes in 2025 and nearly 2–3 tonnes in 2050 (higher with the constant-EF). Introducing heat pumps reduces the mean, while adding PVs lowers both the median and the upper tails, bringing the mean to roughly 1.5–3 tonnes. Envelope renovations further reduce emissions; TS with heat pumps delivers additional reductions, and the TS+HP+ PV drives

the mean sharply downward to about 1 tonne. Passivhaus renovations push emissions toward the lowest levels and coupling them with PV provides consistently nearly zero values, with Passivhaus envelope + HP + PV frequently falling below 1 tonne CO₂. Overall, if the expected decrease in the electricity emission factor (EF) is realized, electrification will lead to significant reductions in overall emissions. However, if this decline does not occur and the EF remains constant as a worst-case scenario, the increasing electricity demand projected for 2050 could result in higher total emissions compared to 2025. Key takeaways:

- Without improvement in the grid emission factor of electricity, emissions in 2050 will be equal to today's emissions.
- With constant grid emission factors, rising energy consumption is projected to exceed the contribution of PVs, resulting in higher emissions.
- To reduce the electricity emission factor, policy implementations must promote a cleaner grid by increasing the share of renewable energy sources.

Figure 13. Annual carbon emission by scenario constant electricity emission factor for 2025 and 2050.

Figure 14. Annual carbon emissions by scenario

4.2.4 PV-based electricity production

A comparative analysis of PV-based electricity production (Figure 15) indicates a projected 6% increase between 2025 and 2050, primarily driven by rising solar radiation levels. This upward trend suggests that future building energy systems could increasingly benefit from enhanced on-site renewable energy generation.

Figure 15. PV-based electricity production

4.2.5 Electricity Self-Sufficiency Index by Scenario

The average annual PV electricity production for buildings is projected to increase slightly from 18.7 MW in 2025 to 19.8 MW in 2050. The distribution of the electricity self-sufficiency index for various renovation scenarios in 2025 and 2050 is shown on Figure 16. Initially, the scenarios employing fossil-fuel-based heating (Baseline, ENVE_{TS}, and ENVE_{PAS}), which exclude the substantial heating load from the total electricity demand, exhibit deceptively high self-sufficiency, approximately 80–81% in 2025 and 75–78% in 2050. These values are not indicative of high self-sufficiency and must be viewed with caution, as buildings’ heating demand is met not by electricity but by natural gas.

The scenarios involving heat pumps (HP) consider heating energy consumption as part of the total electricity energy load, showing the self-sufficiency index as 52% in 2025 and 58% in 2050 for the HP + PV scenario. The index rises from 64-69% to 67-72% for the ENVE_{TS} + HP + PV and ENVE_{PAS} + HP + PV scenarios from 2025 to 2050. This positive trend in which the combined scenarios of envelope renovations and HP demonstrate the highest achievable self-sufficiency in fully electrified systems.

Figure 16. Electricity self-sufficiency index for various renovation scenarios in 2025 and 2050

4.2.6 Indoor Overheating Degree

The evaluation of IOD (Figure 17), focuses only on the TS and Passivhaus scenarios, as HP and PV integration does not directly influence overheating risk. From 2025 to 2050, the Baseline scenario

shows a consistent upward trend, with mean IOD value increasing nearly fivefold, highlighting the growing threat of overheating under future climates.

A closer look at the renovation scenarios shows that in 2025, TS insulation almost halves the Baseline mean, while Passivhaus insulation reduces it to nearly zero. By 2050, however, TS insulation remains limited, lowering the mean IOD by only about 16%, whereas Passivhaus insulation achieves a 77% reduction.

In 2050, while the Baseline reveals increasing overheating with mean IOD value reaching more than 3 times its initial level, the insulation strategies demonstrate clear mitigation potential. Passivhaus envelope insulation performs best in both years, keeping overheating close to lower levels in 2025 and maintaining its effectiveness by 2050.

Figure 17. Indoor Overheating Degree (IOD) for 2025 and 2050

4.2.7 Percentage of Zones Over the Years for Different Scenarios

The risk of overheating can be assessed using the CIBSE (The Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers) overheating risk test, which classifies a living space as failed if the number of overheated hours exceeds 3% of the occupied hours (Figure 18). In the baseline scenario, about 85% of non-air-conditioned living spaces fulfil the CIBSE overheating criteria in 2020, but by 2050 and 2080, this percentage is 54% and 32%, respectively. Energy renovation scenarios help to delay the year in which the overheating risk materializes in some cases.

Figure 18. Percentage of RES zones passed over the years for different scenarios

4.2.8 Delayed Overheating

The distribution of the number of years by which overheating is delayed because of the renovation scenarios for TS825 and Passivhaus can be seen in Figure 19. It shows the shift towards long delay periods when renovated with TS825 standards and even longer delay periods when fulfilling the Passivhaus standards.

Indoor overheating must be evaluated alongside energy performance, as it poses parallel comfort and health challenges. TS and Passivhaus strategies reveal that insulation quality determines resilience, demanding joint assessment of energy and indoor thermal performance.

Figure 19. Delayed overheating of the renovation scenarios for TS825 (left) and Passivhaus (right)

4.2.9 Scenario Based Costs: CAPEX, OPEX and Total Costs (EUR)

In Figure 20, ROI shows the inverse relationship between Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX). In the baseline scenario, costs are only due to OPEX, around €225 million. PV scenario reaching one of the lowest total costs, around €121 million. However, adding only the HP systems drives both CAPEX and OPEX upward, with total expenditures nearly €295 million, as electricity demand increases. The most effective strategy is the ENVETS + PV scenario, the lowest total cost, approximately €120 million. Although Passivhaus renovations offer long-term emission reductions more effectively than the TS insulations, they also require a higher initial investment. Key takeaways:

- Under the tiered electricity tariffs, electrification of heating pushes total consumption above threshold limits and significantly increases electricity bills, making heat pump integration economically unfeasible.
- Super-insulated buildings (i.e. Passivhaus) demand almost twice the initial investment compared to standard insulation. This scenario becomes economically and environmentally justified only when the objective is to reach Nearly Zero-Energy Building (NZEB) performance levels.
- Electrification of heating systems becomes economically feasible only in PV-combined scenarios, due to the electricity tariff implementation.

Figure 20. Scenario based costs: CAPEX, OPEX and total costs (EUR)

4.2.10 NPV and ROI by Scenario

The NPV and ROI distributions show that combining PV with Baseline and ENVE_{TS} scenarios are economically advantageous, showing median NPVs at or above zero and median ROIs between 20–60% (Figure 21). In contrast, HP alone and most Passivhaus scenarios remain financially unattractive: NPVs are predominantly negative, and median ROIs are below zero, even when PV or HP is added. All scenarios with PV systems, particularly the ENVE_{TS}+ PV scenario, offer the most compelling economic returns. Envelope renovations combined with HP, without PV integration, ENVE_{TS} + HP and ENVE_{PAS}+ HP, exhibit the weakest performance.

Figure 21. NPV & ROI by scenario

4.2.11 Payback Survival Curves by Scenario

On Figure 22, it can be observed that in the baseline scenario with PV, half of the buildings achieve payback in under 10 years. Adding PV to HP and TS envelope renovations similarly reduces the mean payback time to around 12–15 years. In contrast, scenarios such as ENVE_{TS} + HP renovations show a more gradual decline in payback probability, with the mean payback not reached within 25 years. Passivhaus scenarios, even with HP, demonstrate a slower financial return, with over 80% of projects not recovering their initial investment within two decades. The Discounted Payback Period allows users to balance long-term sustainability goals with realistic financial timelines.

- If the initial capital is limited, PV system installation is the most feasible approach, followed by adding TS insulation. This combination provides faster financial returns while maintaining acceptable energy performance.
- To achieve financial return over a 25-year period, scenarios that include PV systems should be prioritized.

Figure 22. Payback survival curves by scenario

4.2.12 Marginal Abatement Cost Curve by Scenario

The Abatement Cost (Figure 23) shows the cost-efficiency of carbon reductions across scenarios. The graph illustrates a clear trade-off between reduction potential and cost per ton of CO₂ abated. On the x-axis, the graph shows the CO₂ reduction potential, while the y-axis indicates the abatement cost. According to the results, **PV** offers the lowest abatement cost at approximately **€82** per ton CO₂, with a total reduction of around **0.5** million tons. The integration of PV generally increases the unit cost slightly but significantly increases the total avoided emissions. For instance, adding PV to HP raises abatement costs marginally but extends the total reduction to over **1.0** million tons. Similarly, ENVE_{TS} + PV balances moderate costs with larger reduction potential. While ENVETS insulation alone is more expensive than HP or PV scenarios, combined scenarios like ENVE_{TS} + HP + PV yield higher emission savings at rising costs. Passivhaus-level insulation stands out as the most expensive one, with ENVE_{PAS} + HP reaching nearly **€182** per ton of CO₂, about twice as costly as the HP scenario.

- Although PV integration offers the most cost-effective outcome in terms of emission abatement, its emission reduction remains lower than other combined scenarios.
- If insulation scenarios are not preferred, a combined HP + PV scenario may represent a cost-effective alternative in terms of abatement cost.
- When the main objective is emission reduction, combined scenarios deliver the highest overall performance. Among these, the Passivhaus configuration with HP and PV systems performs slightly better, owing to its higher insulation capacity.

Figure 23. Marginal abatement cost curve by scenario

4.3 Circular Urban Planning application to Alvalade neighbourhood in Lisbon

The tool was applied to the Alvalade neighbourhood in Lisbon. The buildings concerned are from the municipality and consist in university building and a market. The city provided data such as a shape file, building height, perimeter, and year of construction. However, for such studies, it is mandatory to have the material quantities of the building. As those data were not available, identification of materials through computer vision was tried.

The Chair of circular engineering for architecture (Raghu et al. 2022, Raghu et al. 2023) uses tools built upon computer vision and AI to identify building characteristics from photographic sources including publicly available imagery such as Google Street View. These technologies enable the collection of more reliable data, enhancing the accuracy and quality of analysis. However, in our case study, few images of low quality were available which made necessary to add further hypothesis on the material composition of the building.

From these hypotheses and the application of the tool, several results were generated. First, the analysis highlighted which buildings should be prioritized for deconstruction, based on their material composition and potential for reuse as shown in Figure 24. This allows stakeholders to focus efforts on assets that offer the greatest environmental and economic benefits.

Figure 24. Repartition of material emissions from future deconstruction

Second, the results indicated which material supply chains should be developed to maximize GHG emissions reduction. The result is shown in Figure 25. This allows to provide some insights on the future material that will arrive from future deconstruction operations.

Figure 25. Buildings with the most embodied GHG emissions in façades

However, these findings must be interpreted with caution. Due to the limited quality of available imagery and the assumptions made about material composition, further investigation is essential to validate these results. Detailed on-site assessments and standardised diagnostic methods will be necessary to ensure accurate data for decision-making and to strengthen the reliability of circular planning strategies.

Implementation of the tool still faces some challenges. More detailed information on the material is necessary as only hypothesis has been made for now. Also, applying the tool to more building could provide a better overview.

4.4 Impact on Urban Planning and Decision – Making: Alignment with UP2030 Objectives and Cities vision

The integration of BIM and LCA within UP2030 directly supports cities' ambitions for climate neutrality and sustainable urban transformation by providing data-driven insights for retrofitting, resource efficiency, and circularity. These tools enable evidence-based decision-making, aligning with UP2030 objectives of reducing carbon emissions, enhancing resilience, and promoting inclusive urban regeneration. By delivering actionable metrics on energy performance, material reuse, and life-cycle impacts, the project empowers municipalities to prioritize interventions that reflect their long-term vision for liveable, low-carbon cities while fostering.

The metrics selected are defined in order to capture the most relevant dimensions of urban retrofit decision-making, namely energy performance, environmental impact, thermal comfort and economic feasibility. Energy-related KPIs, such as energy consumption per unit area (kWh/m²) are used because they allow consistent comparison across different building types and scales. Environmental indicators, including CO₂ emissions, are selected to directly reflect climate mitigation objectives, while thermal comfort indicators address adaptation and occupant well-being. Economic KPIs, such as payback period, NPV and abatement cost, are included to assess financial feasibility and support prioritisation under budget constraints.

The results of the Istanbul demonstration provide concrete, quantitative evidence to support the prioritisation of urban decarbonisation strategies under different future conditions. The analysis shows that heating demand remains the dominant component of energy consumption across the building stock, although it is projected to decrease by approximately 25% between 2025 and 2050 due to climate change. Envelope improvement scenarios significantly reduce heating demand—by up to a factor of three—while the introduction of heat pumps achieves reductions of up to 77% by shifting demand from natural gas to electricity and benefiting from higher system efficiencies. These findings directly inform planning strategies by identifying envelope retrofitting and electrification as the most impactful levers for reducing operational energy use.

Cooling demand, in contrast, is projected to increase by a factor of approximately 2.3 by 2050 as a result of rising temperatures, highlighting the growing importance of climate adaptation alongside mitigation. The results show that higher insulation standards, particularly Passivhaus-level envelopes, substantially mitigate future overheating risks, reducing IOD by up to 77% in 2050, whereas standard insulation (TS825) offers more limited protection. This evidence supports the prioritisation of higher-performance envelopes in districts exposed to long-term overheating risks, especially in vulnerable residential areas. Emissions analysis further refines intervention prioritisation.

On the other hand, scenarios combining envelope improvements, heat pumps and PV systems consistently achieve the largest CO₂ reductions, with Passivhaus + HP + PV scenarios approaching near-zero emissions at building level when future grid decarbonisation is assumed. However, the results also demonstrate that electrification alone is insufficient if electricity emission factors do not decline. Under constant grid emission factors, rising electricity demand may offset the benefits of electrification, underscoring the need to align building-level interventions with broader energy system decarbonisation policies.

Economic KPIs introduce an additional decision layer. While deep renovation scenarios deliver the highest environmental benefits, they are associated with higher upfront investments and longer payback periods. PV systems emerge as the most cost-effective intervention across scenarios, offering the lowest abatement costs (approximately €80–100 per tCO₂) and the most favourable NPVs and ROIs. Scenarios combining PV with moderate envelope improvements (ENVETS + PV) achieve the lowest total costs and fastest payback times, making them suitable as “no-regret” measures when capital availability is limited. In contrast, Passivhaus-level renovations become economically justified primarily when long-term climate neutrality or near-zero energy building targets are prioritised over short-term financial returns.

By integrating energy, emissions, thermal comfort and economic indicators, the results enable cities to structure phased implementation strategies. Low-cost, high-impact measures such as PV deployment and standard envelope upgrades can be prioritised in the short term, while deeper renovations and full electrification pathways can be scheduled progressively as grid decarbonisation advances and financing conditions improve. This evidence-based prioritisation framework allows municipalities to balance climate ambition, economic feasibility and resilience objectives within coherent urban decarbonisation and adaptation plans.

Beyond the specific case of Istanbul, this pilot illustrates how similar analyses can be applied in other cities to support context-sensitive planning decisions. While absolute values will vary depending on climate, building typologies, energy prices and regulatory frameworks, the comparative interpretation of scenarios enables cities to identify dominant energy drivers, assess trade-offs between mitigation and adaptation, and define locally appropriate combinations of short-term and long-term interventions. The approach demonstrated in the pilot therefore provides a transferable methodology for translating complex analytical results into actionable planning strategies aligned with local priorities and long-term climate goals.

Finally, the visualisation of these results through scenario distributions and comparative indicators supports stakeholder engagement in the planning process. By making trade-offs between energy

savings, emissions reduction, comfort improvement and costs explicit, the tools enable planners, policymakers and non-technical stakeholders to engage in informed discussions and to collectively define intervention priorities aligned with local constraints and long-term climate objectives.

5 Conclusions and recommendations for future work

This deliverable summarises the final version of the bundle of UP2030 digital twin tools into a coherent, interoperable decision-support framework for evidence-based net-zero urban planning. The integration of the UBEM–AI engine, the LCA module and the MIRA Digital Twin platform demonstrates how energy modelling, environmental impact assessment and user-oriented visualisation can be combined within a single analytical workflow supported by a shared data environment. In parallel, the Circular Urban Planning tool extends the scope of analysis beyond operational performance, enabling cities to address material stocks, reuse potential and circularity strategies as part of long-term urban transformation.

A key contribution of this integration during UP2030 project is the ability to move beyond fragmented analyses and isolated modelling exercises. By integrating UBEM, LCA and MIRA through harmonised data structures and a centralised database, cities can consistently evaluate renovation and transition scenarios across multiple dimensions, including energy demand, emissions, thermal comfort and economic performance. This integration improves transparency, traceability and comparability of results, enabling stakeholders to understand trade-offs between short-term gains and long-term impacts, as well as between operational savings and embodied emissions.

The Istanbul demonstration provides a robust proof-of-concept of these benefits. The integrated workflow enabled the assessment of 2,455 buildings under a common scenario framework, revealing how combinations of envelope standards, electrification and PV systems influence energy use, CO₂ emissions, overheating risk and economic feasibility at both building and district scale. Importantly, the results highlighted systemic dependencies—such as the critical role of electricity grid decarbonisation—showing that building-level interventions must be interpreted within a broader energy system context. This type of insight is only achievable through integrated, multi-tool analysis.

The Circular Urban Planning tool further strengthens the evidence base by addressing resource efficiency and circularity. Although currently implemented as a standalone application, its results complement the energy- and emissions-focused analyses by identifying priority materials, buildings and supply chains for selective deconstruction and reuse. Together, these tools illustrate how cities can adopt a more holistic planning perspective that combines decarbonisation, climate adaptation and circular economy objectives.

The implementation and scaling of digital twin–based decision-support systems require governance frameworks that extend beyond technical integration. Cities must define clear responsibilities for data management, model maintenance and scenario validation, including rules for data ownership, access rights, quality control and versioning. Transparent governance arrangements are essential to ensure that modelling outputs can be confidently used in policy formulation, investment planning and regulatory processes. Institutional coordination is equally important. The effective use of the UP2030 toolkit depends on collaboration across municipal departments responsible for urban planning, energy, climate policy, housing, finance and procurement. Without such coordination, digital twin outputs risk remaining isolated technical artefacts rather than being translated into concrete implementation measures. Embedding the use of these tools within formal planning cycles, climate action plans and monitoring frameworks is therefore a critical step toward long-term impact.

However, experience from the UP2030 cities confirms that municipalities require technical capacity to curate and harmonise spatial, building and material datasets; analytical capacity to interpret scenario-based KPIs; and organisational capacity to integrate evidence into decision-making workflows.

The major constraint is data availability and quality. Many cities lack consistent, centralised datasets describing building geometry, construction characteristics, systems and materials. As a result, significant effort is often required for manual data collection, harmonisation and validation, drawing from multiple sources with varying levels of reliability. Greater availability of BIM-based datasets would significantly enhance automation, reduce uncertainty and accelerate analysis workflows. While

it is recognised that comprehensive BIM models are not yet widely available at city scale, their progressive adoption would substantially reduce manual data handling, improve interoperability and support more dynamic and scalable digital twin implementations. Similarly, the Circular Urban Planning application in Lisbon illustrates how limited or inferred material data introduce uncertainty, underlining the importance of improved material inventories and diagnostic methods for reliable CAs.

Based on the experience gained in the UP2030 Project, replication should follow a phased and context-sensitive approach related to:

- Data readiness and harmonisation: establish a minimum viable dataset aligned with the shared data model, prioritising consistent identifiers, metadata and basic building typologies.
- Context-specific scenario definition: tailor renovation and transition scenarios to local regulations, construction practices, energy prices and tariff structures, as these strongly influence economic and environmental outcomes.
- Policy and system alignment: interpret building-level electrification and renewable scenarios with local and national grid decarbonisation trajectories and policy frameworks.
- Progressive integration of circularity: strengthen material data availability and gradually link CAs with energy and LCA workflows to avoid burden shifting and support holistic decision-making.

Future work should focus on advancing the UP2030 toolkit from an integration proof-of-concept toward a more automated, adaptive and scalable planning environment. Key research directions include deeper integration of circularity and energy/LCA analyses, systematic uncertainty and sensitivity assessment, enhanced automation through BIM and real-time data streams, and user-centred refinement of KPIs for policy, budgeting and procurement processes. Developing reusable replication packages—covering data schemas, governance roles, documentation and training materials—would further reduce entry barriers for cities and support long-term sustainability.

In summary, the UP2030 digital tool bundle demonstrates a credible and transferable pathway for cities to operationalise evidence-based planning toward climate neutrality. Its impact depends not only on technical interoperability but also on governance structures, institutional capacity, stakeholder engagement and data maturity. Addressing these dimensions in parallel will be essential to scale the approach and to support cities in designing locally adapted, robust and socially accepted net-zero transformation strategies.

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